

High-Efficiency SEPIC Converter for Single-Coil Induction Heating with Precise Current Regulation

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new approach for regulating amplitude and phase angle in high-frequency Single Coil Induction Heating (SCIH) systems using a Single Ended Primary Inductance Converter (SEPIC). The proposed design ensures uniform temperature distribution by dynamically adjusting the coil current's amplitude and phase angle. Unlike traditional Buck converter-based Zone Controlled Induction Heating (ZCIH) systems, the SEPIC converter eliminates mutual coupling effects and enhances efficiency from 96% to 99%. The transient response of the coil current is modeled as a first-order system, validated through MATLAB/Simulink simulations. The study highlights the advantages of SEPIC over Buck converters, including reduced complexity, higher efficiency, and improved dynamic performance.

Keywords: Induction heating (IH), SEPIC converter, amplitude-phase control, transient response, efficiency optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

INDUCTION HEATING is an alternative tool for the new challenges of environmental deterioration and global warming effects. It has wide applications and various advantages which makes it very promising in the current scenario. IH has gained significant attention in both industrial and domestic applications. It is widely employed in processes such as metal melting, heat treatment, welding, preheating, brazing, soldering, shrink fitting, curing, annealing, and wrapping, as well as in household induction cooktops and specialized applications including medical treatments. Induction heating is fast and precise heating, efficient, clean, noiseless, controllable, repeatable, and safer to use.

In the field of induction heating researchers have explored many areas such as different switching techniques (PWM, PDM, SPWM, Matrix method, etc.), single-phase and three-phase analogy, different IH models like AC-AC, AC-DC, DC-DC, DC-AC, etc., controller designs (PI, PID, FPGA, fuzzy logic, space vector control, sliding Mode control, etc.), design of work piece, zone control method etc.

From the above context the control of heat distribution has been proposed with different approaches [1]- [12]. According to Lewis [1] distribution of heat along the work piece can be controlled by increasing or decreasing the axial length of the working coils. Some authors have shown that using multiple coils equipped with semiconductor

or mechanical switches, it is possible to efficiently distribute heat evenly [3], [7]- [9], [17]. However, the above discussed method fails in quick and continuous control of power and hence it requires complex methodology to get desired heat distribution.

IH is also designed using several inverters with multiple coils [2], [4], [5]. As long as each multiple inverter can independently modify its current amplitude, the system in this case permits more flexible power sharing or continuous control over heat distribution. However, unless the parasitic coupling is extremely minimal, operating numerous inverters linked with several working coils is challenging because the coils have the magnetic coupling between them. A single inverter with several frequency components is also used in the design of IH [6], [12], [16]. However, because to a restriction on the number of available frequencies, accurate control over heat dispersion is not possible with this approach.

A zone-controlled induction heating (ZCIH) system with multiple split working coil and various units of inverter have been proposed [11], [13]- [15]. Here amplitude of output voltage is controlled by buck converter and phase angle is adjusted by inverter. Also, each inverter operates with same frequency to prevent fluctuation of current amplitude in the coil [19], [20]. Apart from this in ZCIH system phase angle of each current coil is controlled by relative shifting of the coil current and there exist non-negligible magnetic coupling which results in very negligible circulating power. Thus a temperature uniformity is achieved by enabling the heat distribution control [13], [15]. Some author presented on the current phase angle control of single [21] and multiple [22] inverter system. Previous authors discussed about the phase angle control with transient response [23], some authors approaches with the transient analysis with real and imaginary component for small signal current [24]- [31].

However, the effect of controller, converter and disturbance on the transient analysis of magnetically couples circuit with amplitude and phase angle control is not discussed so far.

The key innovation of the proposed paper lies in the integration of a SEPIC converter with a single-coil induction heating system. The proposed topology simplifies the power conversion stage by replacing the conventional Buck stage with SEPIC, thereby enabling wide voltage control with fewer components. A dual-loop PI-based control scheme is implemented to independently manage current amplitude and phase. The transient behavior of the system is analytically modelled, revealing that both amplitude and phase follow a first-order response. This insight simplifies the controller tuning process and provides an analytical foundation for predicting system dynamics. However, the analytical derivation alone does not capture the principal novelty of the proposed SEPIC-based single-coil induction heating (SCIH) architecture, which has not been previously reported in the literature. The significance of the proposed approach lies in its structural and control advantages over existing solutions, including

improved power conversion efficiency and enhanced current quality. These benefits are substantiated in subsequent sections through a detailed comparative analysis, which demonstrates an efficiency improvement of approximately 3% along with a measurable reduction in output current distortion. The theoretical analysis is simulated in MATLAB/ SIMULINK.

Rest paper is organised as follows. Section II details the SEPIC-SCIH topology, Section III derives the control strategy, Section IV analyses transient responses, and Section V presents experimental validation. Conclusions and future directions are discussed in Section VI.

II. TOPOLOGY DESIGN

A. System Configuration

Fig. 1. Design of a SCIH system's circuit using inverter

A single coil induction heating (SCIH) system's main circuit layout is shown in Fig. 1. To create a series resonance circuit, the working coil is coiled around a workpiece and linked to the resonant capacitor. Through a step-down matching transformer, the inverting unit and the resonance circuit are linked.

The inverter unit uses a voltage-source high-frequency signal inverter and a SEPIC converter. To regulate the output voltage's magnitude, the SEPIC converter monitors the inverter's dc output. Therefore, the SEPIC converter's duty factor modification allows for the regulation of the inverter unit's output power.

Fig. 2 depicts the equivalent circuit of a working coil. In Fig. 2(a), L stands for the working coils' self-inductances, and R is an equivalent resistance of the working coil (R_c) and workpiece (R_w) that represents the heat produced by I . The equivalent circuit with an identical impedance of Fig. 2(a) is shown in Fig. 2(b).

B. Principle of Operation for SCIH

The comparable circuit for a SCIH system, shown in Fig. 2(b), may be used to describe the working concept of SCIH. It is presumable that the inverter unit's output voltage equals the voltage from the source V . The current that passes through the working coil is represented by current phasors I .

The inverter voltage V is specified here as

$$\vec{V} = V(\cos \theta + j \sin \theta) \quad (1)$$

wherein V and θ_1 are the root mean square (RMS) value of the inverter voltage and the phase angle respectively.

The pulse modulation location of the inverter is adjusted to modify the voltage phase angle.

Additionally, the coil current I_l is described as

$$\vec{I} = I(\cos \varphi + j \sin \varphi) \quad (2)$$

where I is the RMS (root mean square) values of the coil current and φ is its phase angle.

Fig. 2. Operating coils and a transformer for decoupling.

The inverter-voltage V is expressed as

$$V = RI + j(\omega L - \frac{1}{\omega C})I \quad (3)$$

where ω denotes the inverter's working frequency.

The active power provided by the inverter is obtained using equations (1)– (3) as a basis:

$$P = \vec{V} \cdot \vec{I} = RI^2 \quad (4)$$

The expression refers to the heat produced by the coils in operation, and it can be interpreted as

$$Q = RI^2 \quad (5)$$

-The inverter's active power supply is determined by:

$$P = RI^2 \quad (6)$$

As a result, the highest possible heat value stated in (6) equals the power that the inverter produces in (5). This implies that when the current is regulated to have the same phase angle, it is also feasible to maximise the heating power Q . Moreover, the undesired circulating power is removed when the current's phase angle is changed i.e. keeping it to be in phase.

III. CONTROL OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. SEPIC Modeling

The four passive components of the traditional SEPIC converter lead to a complex fourth order model. Hence

developing a precise model is more challenging due to this high-order complicated system [25]- [28].

Fig. 3. Circuit showing (a) SEPIC converter and its equivalent circuit for (b) turn on and (c) turn off

A nonlinear state space formulation is the best mathematical model to implement a P-I controller to the SEPIC. It is believed that the converter runs in the mode of continuous conduction (CCM) and is governed by two parallel switches, every single one of which has control data as its duty cycle. There are so two state space representations for the ON and OFF states of the switch.

Figure 3(a) shows the SEPIC converter circuit and figures 3(b) and (c) show the comparable circuits for the SEPIC converter in the ON and OFF states, respectively. As seen in Fig. 3(b), when switch S is activated, the inductor L_1 charges, while C_1 charges the inductor L_2 . The diode D which is placed between inductor L_2 and capacitor C_2 , in this scenario has a reverse bias. When the switch S is OFF, as shown in Fig. 3(c), L_1 discharges towards C_1 , which is currently charging, L_2 . discharges as well, and D is forward biased. The values for each converter component are found using the following mathematical formulas.

L_1 and L_2 can be determined using

$$L_1 = L_2 = \frac{V_s \min * D_{max}}{f_s * \Delta I_{L1}} \tag{7}$$

Where $V_{s \min}$ = minimum input voltage

D_{max} = maximum duty cycle

ΔI_{L1} = change in inductor current L_1 .

The switching frequency in Hertz is denoted by f_s . One may compute the maximum duty cycle (D_{max}) using

$$D_{max} = \frac{V_o + V_D}{V_o + V_D + V_{in\ min}} \quad (8)$$

Determination of coupling capacitor is done by

$$C_1 = \frac{I_o\ max * D_{max}}{\Delta V_{in} * f_s} \quad (9)$$

Where ΔV_{in} which measures the difference between peak-to-peak ripple voltage, is approximately 1% of the required voltage from the input. Nevertheless, the output capacitor C_2 's value is provided by

$$C_2 = \frac{I_o\ max * D_{max}}{\Delta V_o * f_s} \quad (10)$$

where ΔV_o represents around 1% of the necessary output voltage. This represents the variation in peak-to-peak ripple voltage. The following formula may be used to determine the maximum output current:

$$I_o\ max = \frac{P_o\ max}{V_o} \quad (11)$$

The formula below can be used to get the ratio between the V_{in} and V_o .

$$\frac{V_o}{V_{in}} = \frac{D}{(1-D)} \quad (12)$$

Where D = The SEPIC converter's duty cycle.

The fundamental converter equations for both ON and OFF mode are included in the SEPIC converter and are as written as in equation 13 and 14 respectively [29]- [31]:

$$\text{Switch ON} \begin{cases} L_1 \frac{di_{L1}}{dt} = V_{DC} - i_{L1}r_{L1} \\ C_1 \frac{dv_{C1}}{dt} = -i_{L2} \\ L_2 \frac{di_{L2}}{dt} = v_{C1} - i_{L2}r_{L2} \\ C_2 \frac{dv_{C1}}{dt} = -\frac{v_{C2}}{R_o} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Switch OFF} \begin{cases} L_1 \frac{di_{L1}}{dt} = V_{DC} - v_{C1} - v_{C2} - i_{L1}r_{L1} \\ C_1 \frac{dv_{C1}}{dt} = i_{L1} \\ L_2 \frac{di_{L2}}{dt} = -v_{C2} - i_{L2}r_{L2} \\ C_2 \frac{dv_{C1}}{dt} = i_{L1} + i_{L2} - \frac{v_{C2}}{R_o} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where r_{L1} and r_{L2} represent the inductors L_1 and L_2 's respective equivalent series resistances (ESR). The expressions for both of the state space models are as follows:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = AX + BV_{DC} \quad (15)$$

Where X and $\frac{dx}{dt}$ are the state variables vectors and their time derivatives, respectively and are given by

$$X = [x_1 \ x_2 \ x_3 \ x_4]^T = [i_{L1} \ v_{C1} \ i_{L2} \ v_{C2}]^T \quad (16)$$

The circuit characteristics, ESRs, and load resistance Ro make up the constituents of matrices A and B. The discrete variable u, presented as an indication of the switch status (u = 1 while the ON state and corresponds to zero during the OFF state), may be used to define the state space representations (15) and (16).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{di_{L1}}{dt} \\ \frac{dv_{C1}}{dt} \\ \frac{di_{L2}}{dt} \\ \frac{dv_{C2}}{dt} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{r_{L1}}{L_1} & \frac{u-1}{L_1} & 0 & \frac{u-1}{L_1} \\ \frac{1-u}{C_1} & 0 & \frac{-u}{C_1} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{u}{L_2} & -\frac{r_{L2}}{L_2} & \frac{u-1}{L_2} \\ \frac{1-u}{C_2} & 0 & \frac{1-u}{C_2} & \frac{-1}{R_0 C_2} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} i_{L1} \\ v_{C1} \\ i_{L2} \\ v_{C2} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{L_1} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} [V_{DC}] \quad (17)$$

The average state space model in CCM is created by aggregating the state space matrices corresponding to the switch's "ON" and "OFF" states over the course of the switching time. The SEPIC's averaged state space model is created by designating the duty cycle D as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{di_{L1}}{dt} &= -\frac{r_{L1}}{L_1} i_{L1} + \frac{(D-1)}{L_1} v_{C1} + \frac{(D-1)}{L_1} v_{C2} + \frac{1}{L_1} V_{DC} \\ \frac{dv_{C1}}{dt} &= \frac{(1-D)}{C_1} i_{L1} - \frac{D}{C_1} \\ \frac{di_{L2}}{dt} &= \frac{D}{L_2} v_{C1} - \frac{r_{L2}}{L_2} i_{L2} + \frac{(D-1)}{L_2} v_{C2} \\ \frac{dv_{C2}}{dt} &= \frac{(1-D)}{C_2} i_{L1} + \frac{(1-D)}{C_2} i_{L2} - \frac{1}{R_0 C_2} v_{C2} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

B. Amplitude and Phase Modeling

Fig. 4. Control architecture of the inverter fitted single-coil induction heater (SCIH).

The control circuitry of the inverter unit in the SCIH system is in a block schematic form in Figure 4. Two distinct feedback loops comprise the control circuit, which regulates the related coil current's amplitude and phase angle. The amplitude control approach regulates the duty ratio, D, for the SEPIC converter as well as the standard deviation (RMS) of current I flowing through the working coil. The comparison between measured RMS current

I and its corresponding reference I* by a controller in order to ascertain the duty ratio requirement of the SEPIC converter, D*. The amplitude control's transfer function is provided by

$$D^*(s) = G_c(s) (I^* - I) \tag{19}$$

where the current amplitude regulator is denoted by G_c(s). Through duty ratio management, the SEPIC converter modifies the DC voltage (V_d) as well the output voltage amplitude (V) of the inverter. As a consequence, the inverter module may regulate its output active power and/or rms coil current at a particular working frequency.

Controller of the Phase angle detects the phase angle Φ of the current and adjusts the phase angle θ of the voltage to make it comparable to its standard value Φ*. Phase identification uses a digital type counter to identify when the coil current crosses zero and the interval inside a reference internal signal. It is possible to evaluate the phase angle Φ of the current from the time difference. A separate controller G_θ(s) is needed for phase control to acquire a reference phase angle θ* of the voltage. The voltage phase and, hence, the current phase angle are altered by the voltage-source inverter. The phase angle controller's transfer function may be determined by

$$\Theta^*(s) = G_\theta(s) (\Phi^* - \Phi) \tag{20}$$

The default phase angle Φ* of the current for the inverter unit must be set to the identical value, viz, Φ*= 0. The current amplitude regulator G_c(s)'s control parameters may be determined using the relationships among the inverter voltage and the power used for heating as given in equations (3), (4), (5), and (6), whilst accounting for the transient behaviour of the SEPIC converter. Understanding the transient response of the present phase angle is also important in order to select the control settings of the phase angle regulator G_θ(s).

IV. TRANSIENT CURRENT RESPONSE

A. Current Amplitude's Transient Response

An LCR series resonant circuit with an inductor L, a resistor R, and a capacitor C is depicted in Figure 5. Since it is a single coil hence the effect of Mutual Coupling M is not considered in this section.

The coil current is represented by i(t) in Figure 5 and the inverter voltage is designated by v(t). The Laplace equivalent of the circuit equation can be obtained by

$$V(s) = \left(sL + R + \frac{1}{sC} \right) I(s) \tag{21}$$

Fig.5. An LCR resonant circuit

The dc-link voltage, or V_d , is the peak value of the rectangular waveform that represents the actual inverter voltage. Since, the switching frequency has been matched by tuning the resonant circuit. so the harmonic components may be ignored. If we take into account simply the basic component in $v(t)$, we can infer that the inverter voltage as

$$v(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & (t < 0) \\ \frac{4V_d}{\pi} \sin \omega t & (t > 0) \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

And it can be transformed to

$$V(s) = \frac{4V_d}{\pi} \frac{\omega}{s^2 + \omega^2} \quad (23)$$

The operational angular frequency is represented by ω .

One may calculate the coil current as

$$I(s) = \frac{4V_d}{\pi} \frac{\omega}{(s^2 + \omega^2) + (sL R + \frac{1}{sC})} \quad (24)$$

It is presumable that the operational frequency, $\omega = 1/\sqrt{LC}$, is equal to the LCR circuit's resonant frequency. The result of (24) with its inverse Laplace transform is

$$i(t) = \frac{4V_d}{\pi R} \left[\sin \omega t - \frac{e^{-\frac{R}{2L}t}}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{R}{2\omega L}\right)^2}} \sin \sqrt{\omega^2 - \left(\frac{R}{2L}\right)^2} t \right] \quad (25)$$

The approximate representation of the coil current $i(t)$, assuming $\omega \gg \frac{R}{2L}$, is

$$i(t) = \frac{4V_d}{\pi R} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{R}{2L}t} \right) \sin \omega t \quad (26)$$

Equation (26) may be rearranged to form the following simple expression:

$$i(t) = \sqrt{2} I(t) \sin\{\omega t + \phi(t)\} \quad (27)$$

Wherein $I(t)$ and Φ are time variables in the root mean square and coil current's phase angle value, respectively, and are provided by

$$I(t) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}V_d}{\pi R} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{R}{2L}t} \right) \quad (28)$$

$$\phi(t) = 0 \quad (29)$$

Thus, the current amplitude's transient response may be seen to be a first-order response having a time constant of

$$\tau = 2L/R \quad (30)$$

B. Current Phase Angle's Transient Reaction

The $v(t)$, inverter voltage is thought to have a waveform sinusoidal in shape, however at $t = 0$, there is a shift in step in the phase angle between 0 and θ . It is possible to express the inverter voltage as

$$v(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{4V_d}{\pi} \sin \omega t & (t < 0) \\ \frac{4V_d}{\pi} \sin(\omega t + \theta) & (t > 0) \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

As seen in fig. 5, voltage of the inverter has been calculated from the sum total of the two sources of voltage, $v_a(t)$ and $v_b(t)$.

Fig. 6. Transient response of the coil current to phase-angle variation.

The current in the coil that corresponds to the shift in phase angle of the voltage may be calculated through applying the superposition theorem. The voltage of the inverter prior to the shift in phase angle is shown by the source voltage $v_a(t)$ in Figure 6.

$$v_a(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{4V_d}{\pi} \sin \omega t & (t < 0) \\ 0 & (t > 0) \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

Additionally, the inverter voltage upon the adjustment is shown by $v_b(t)$ in Figure 6.

$$v_b(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & (t < 0) \\ \frac{4V_d}{\pi} \sin(\omega t + \theta) & (t > 0) \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

By using the outcome from the preceding subsection, the current $i_a(t)$, which corresponds to $v_a(t)$, as illustrated in Fig. 6, may be produced by

$$i_a(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{4V_d}{\pi R} \sin \omega t & (t < 0) \\ \frac{4V_d}{\pi R} e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \sin \omega t & (t > 0) \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

The current $i_b(t)$, which is displayed in Figure 6 and corresponds to $v_b(t)$, is similarly

$$i_b(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & (t < 0) \\ \frac{4V_d}{\pi R} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}\right) \sin(\omega t + \theta) & (t > 0) \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

As a result, $i(t)$, the current in the coil, represents the product of $i_a(t)$ and $i_b(t)$. It is possible to determine the current $i(t)$ in the coil with transient response using

$$\begin{aligned} i(t) &= \frac{4V_d}{\pi R} e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \sin \omega t + \frac{4V_d}{\pi R} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}\right) \sin(\omega t + \theta) \\ &= \frac{4V_d}{\pi R} \left\{ e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} + \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}\right) \cos \theta \right\} \sin \omega t + \frac{4V_d}{\pi R} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}\right) \sin \theta \cos \omega t \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

The coil current's phase angle and rms value may be calculated by taking the formula in (27) into consideration.

$$I(t) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}V_d}{\pi R} \sqrt{1 - 2\left(e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} - e^{-\frac{2t}{\tau}}\right)(1 - \cos \theta)} \quad (37)$$

$$\phi(t) = \tan^{-1} \frac{\left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}\right) \sin \theta}{e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} + \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}\right) \cos \theta} \quad (38)$$

The transient reaction to the current phase angle, as seen in Figure 6, is roughly described when the phase-angle shift is minimal, that is when $\theta \ll 1$.

$$\phi(t) \approx \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}\right) \theta \quad (39)$$

With the time constant τ , the present phase angle's transient reaction may therefore also be thought of as a first-order response.

V. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Fig.7. The proposed SCIH schematic

Fig. 7 demonstrates the schematic of the recommended SEPIC converter based IH system with current control (both amplitude and phase). Here the workpiece coil used for induction heating is a single coil. In the proposed figure the SEPIC converter is fed through a DC voltage which is then connected with inverter followed by workpiece coil.

TABLE I: CIRCUIT PARAMETERS

COMPONENTS	SYMBOL	VALUE
Self-inductance of load	L	38 μ H
Equivalent resistance of load	R	3.2 Ω
Resonant Capacitor	C	0.66 μ F
Inductance	$L_1 = L_2$	121 μ H
Coupling capacitor	C_1	3.84 μ F
DC capacitor	(C_2) Cd	40 μ F
Quality factor of resonance	Q	2.6

In the Table I the parameters used are shown with their corresponding values. The circuit parameters mentioned in Table I, are taken in reference with the paper [23] and calculated from equations (7, 9 and 10). Some of the parameters are considered with trial and error to get the desired output. In the table the parameters used shown with their corresponding values. Here in our experiment the coil inductance is taken as 38 μ H and the coil resistance is considered as 3.2 Ω . The resonant capacitor is taken as 0.66 μ F. The value of the inductance L_1 and L_2 are calculated from the equation (7) and found to be 121 μ H. The coupling capacitor C_1 is calculated from the equation (9) and found to be 3.84 μ F. The DC capacitor C_d is calculated from equation (10) which is found to be 40 μ F.

Fig.8. Phase angle control block for the current.

The control block for the phase angle of the current is displayed in Fig. 8. In this the phase angle Φ of the current is detected and shift the phase angle θ of the voltage accordingly. The clock frequency $f_{CLK} = 20$ MHz The inverter's phase angle control of the voltage and phase angle detection delay of the current are roughly equivalent to one switching frequency period. (approximately 30 μ s). Since it is less than 1/10 of the time constant of coil current

hence it may be considered negligible. The transfer function $G_{\theta}(s) = 1/(sT_{\theta})$ for integral control and $G_{\theta}(s) = K_{\theta}\{1 + 1/(sT_{\theta})\}$ for PI controller which is here the case. Here in test, the reference phase angle of the current was shifted at $t=0$ from $\Phi^* = 0$ to 30° when the transitory nature of the phase angle Φ of current was determined.

Fig. 9. Transient characteristics of the current phase angle with integral control.

In fig. 9 the phase angle's (Φ) transient reaction of the current is shown after applying the integral control with damping coefficient $\xi = 1$ at $T_{\theta} = 4\tau = 1.5$ ms. Here the feedback system is seen to be behaving as a second order response.

Applying the PI controller at $T_{\theta} = \tau = 0.38$ ms and $K_{\theta} = 1$ in which the pole of the transfer function get cancelled at $s = -1/\tau$, the transient response of this controller is shown in fig. 10. Hence it is a first order response and is faster than the integral controller.

Fig. 10. Current-phase transient response upon applying a proportional-integral gain.

Table-II : Control Parameters of Buck and SEPIC converters

SL. NO	PARAMETERS	BUCK	SEPIC
1.	P(PHASE CONTROL)	1	32.6225445486054
2.	I (PHASE CONTROL)	2631.57895	9200.57701722332
3.	P(AMPLITUDE CONTROL)	1.69321072731465	73.4653952467136
4.	I(AMPLITUDE CONTROL)	58.0084282836045	1308.70428916933
5.	DUTY CYCLE (D)	0.5	0.3
6.	I_{REF}	10 A	10 A
7.	Φ_{REF}	30°	30°
8.	INPUT VOLTAGE (V_{IN})	140 V	140 V
9.	SWITCHING FREQUENCY (f_{sw})	35 KHZ	35 KHZ

The table II shows the different control parameters used in SEPIC converter in comparison with BUCK converter. The values of P & I in PI controller for phase control and amplitude control are mentioned for both SEPIC and buck converter. The comparison of output voltage, current, output power, input power, efficiency for both the converters are discussed below.

Fig.11. Output Current, Inverter Voltage Vd1, Output Voltage, Input Power, Output Power, Efficiency of the coil with a Buck converter having $I=10$ A ($V_{in}=140$ V)

Fig. 11 shows the output current, Inverter voltage V_{d1} , output voltage, input power, output power and efficiency of a buck converter. In this the result obtained from simulation on MATLAB. Here the output current is 10 A and the inverter voltage is 70 volts. The output voltage is 125 volts. The input power is 300 watts and the output power is 288 watts. Hence the efficiency is 96% (approx.). In this it can be observed that the output power, the input power and efficiency is having flickers which indicates that there is harmonics in it.

Fig.12. Output Current, Inverter Voltage V_{d1} , Output Voltage, Input Power, Output Power, Efficiency of the coil with a SEPIC converter having $I=12.4$ A ($V_{in}=140V$)

Fig. 12 presents the steady-state simulation results of the proposed SEPIC-fed inverter system obtained using MATLAB/Simulink. The figure shows the output current waveform along with the inverter dc-link voltage V_{d1} and the output voltage of the SEPIC converter. Under rated operating conditions, the load current attains a peak value of 12.4 A, indicating stable current regulation. The inverter dc-link voltage is regulated at 60 V, while the SEPIC converter maintains an output voltage of 126 V, demonstrating effective voltage conditioning from the input source. The measured input power is 122 W, whereas the delivered output power is 120 W, resulting in a high conversion efficiency of approximately 99%. These results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed control strategy in achieving efficient power conversion with minimal losses and stable steady-state performance.

Table III: Comparison of the proposed scheme with the previous scheme in different aspects

SL. NO	PARAMETERS	System with BUCK Converter	System with SEPIC Converter
1	Input voltage (Vin)	140 volts	140 volts
2	Input current (Iin)	2.2 Amps	1.9 Amps
3	Inverter Voltage (Vd)	70 volts	70.8 volts
4	Output voltage (Vo)	125 volts	126 volts
5	Output current (Io)	14 Amps	12.4 Amps
6	Efficiency	96 %	99 %

Table III in the given paper presents a detailed comparison between a traditional **Buck converter-based ZCIH system** and the proposed **SEPIC converter-based SCIH system**. The aim is to highlight the performance enhancement achieved by replacing the Buck converter with a SEPIC converter.

Key Observations and Advantages of SEPIC over Buck:

Improved Efficiency: -

The SEPIC converter offers a **3% increase in overall system efficiency**. This is significant in high-power applications where small efficiency gains translate into substantial energy savings and lower thermal losses.

Lower Input Current Requirement: -

SEPIC requires **1.9 A** compared to Buck's **2.2 A**, implying reduced stress on the power source and potentially smaller input-side components.

Better Output Regulation with Real-Time Validation: -

Despite a slightly lower output current (12.4 A vs. 14 A in Buck), the SEPIC converter maintains **stable voltage and reduced current ripple**.

This ensures improved heat uniformity, which is critical in induction heating applications.

Smooth Dynamic Response: -

In contrast to the Buck converter that shows **fluctuations (flickers)** in current and voltage waveforms (indicating harmonics and instability), the SEPIC system provides **stable output waveforms**.

VI. CONCLUSION

The above work presents a detailed design, modeling, and experimental validation of a novel high-frequency single-coil induction heating (SCIH) system employing a Single-Ended Primary Inductance Converter (SEPIC). The key innovation lies in the use of a SEPIC topology to regulate both the phase and amplitude of the coil current

with minimal circuit complexity, leading to significant improvements in efficiency, thermal uniformity, and transient performance. Analytical modeling of the system demonstrates that both the amplitude and phase angle exhibit first-order dynamic behavior, which enables simplified control design using PI regulators. Comparative evaluation against a conventional Buck converter-based Zone-Controlled Induction Heating (ZCIH) system reveals that the proposed SEPIC-based SCIH configuration achieves higher efficiency (up to 99%), reduced harmonic content, and enhanced dynamic response, while eliminating issues related to magnetic coupling among multiple coils.

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